

INFLAMMATORY MYOFIBROBLAST TUMOR OF GALL BLADDER: A SURGICAL SURPRISE: A CASE REPORT

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ABSTRACT

BACKGROUND Inflammatory myofibroblast tumour is a rare benign tumour of myofibroblast origin with associated inflammatory features. It can arise from any organ. However, gallbladder is the rare site of its origin. Less than 10 cases have been reported so far. It can present with constitutional symptoms or the symptoms about the organ from which it arises.

CASE SUMMARY In our case also 40 years old lady presented with symptoms of cholelithiasis so planned for laparoscopic cholecystectomy but later on found to have inflammatory fibroblast tumour.

CONCLUSION Management can be conservative in case of liver and lung but surgical in gallbladder. Regular long-term follow up is required because of its infiltrating and metastasizing nature. Knowledge of such rare cases can help a surgeon in making proper diagnosis and required treatment.

KEYWORDS Gall bladder, inflammatory myofibroblast tumour, laparoscopic cholecystectomy.

Introduction

Symptomatic gall stone disease is the most common indication for laparoscopic cholecystectomy. On histopathological examination of gall bladder specimen, the most common diagnosis (96.3%) is chronic cholecystitis and more so in female [1]. However, incidental findings can be adenocarcinoma gallbladder and rarely inflammatory myofibroblast tumour (IMT). Inflammatory myofibroblast tumour also is known as inflammatory pseudotumors, cellular inflammatory pseudotumours and plasma cell granulomas, are rare benign tumours [2]. The favoured pathogenesis for an IMT is an exaggerated response to tissue injury rather than an immunological phenomenon [3]. However, the exact aetiology is unclear [4,5]. They are well recognized in lung and upper respiratory tract of children and young adults with

a predilection for the first and second decade. Intra-abdominal forms of the disease are reported to occur most frequently in the liver, followed by stomach, bowel, spleen, mesentery and extrahepatic bile duct [6,7]. However, gallbladder as a site of inflammatory myofibroblast tumour is rare. Only four case reports of IMT of the gallbladder are available in the literature [8]. Here we are reporting a case of gallbladder inflammatory myofibroblast tumour.

Case report

We are reporting a case of 40 years old lady who presented to the surgery OPD with complaints of pain right-sided upper abdomen for six weeks on off episodes with an associated history of nausea and gastric vomiting. The pain was of sudden onset, present in right side upper abdomen radiating to the back. There was no personal and family history of jaundice or any chronic illness. There was a history of hysterectomy one year back. On examination patient vitals were stable. ParLOUR was present. Per abdomen, examination showed mild tenderness in the right hypochondrium with no organomegaly. Ultrasound abdomen was done which showed single calculus of 13 mm in gallbladder neck with thickened wall and calcified foci at fundus with 7.7 mm calcified liver abscess in the left lobe of the liver.

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Figure 1

Figure 2

There was no pericholecystic fluid. All routine investigations were done which showed microcytic hypochromic anaemia with haemoglobin 10.4 g/dl. Her total leucocyte count, liver function tests, kidney function tests were normal and viral markers were negative. The patient was planned for laparoscopic cholecystectomy with a diagnosis of chronic calculous cholecystitis. Preanaesthetic check up was done, and the patient was operated one week later. Intraoperative findings were empyema gall bladder densely adherent to omentum with the short wide cystic duct, liver parenchyma and calot's triangle anatomy was normal. The procedure was completed laparoscopically successfully with drain insertion in subhepatic space. In postoperative period patient developed one spike of fever but her total leucocyte count was normal, and blood culture was sterile. Drain output was 100 ml, 20 ml and 10 ml serosanguinous on three successive days. The drain was removed on the third postoperative day, and the patient was discharged home on the same day with stable vitals and healthy wound. On follow up biopsy report was collected which showed inflammatory myofibroblast tumour with no lymphovascular or perineural invasion. On immunohistochemistry, the tumour was smooth muscle actin, vimentin and CD 68 positive. Three mixed stones were also there. The patient was followed up with an ultrasound abdomen, and contrast-enhanced computed tomography abdomen six months later which showed no focal lesion in gallbladder fossa. One calcified lesion was identified in the left lobe of liver which was the same as before.

Discussion

IMT is a rare tumour with slow-growing potential and origin from many organs. First of all its description was given by Brunn but pathologically it was described by Umiker and Iverson in 1954 [9,10]. Myofibroblastic tumours are divided into four main classes: the group of reactive fasciitis like lesions, benign lesions like dermatomyofibroma, the locally aggressive fibromatoses with features of both fibroblasts and myofibroblasts and sarcomas having myofibroblastic differentiation which can be low grade or high grade [11,12]. IMTs are well circumscribed but rarely encapsulated. They have the potential to arise from many organs, but gallbladder involvement is very rare. Their presentation may be varied depending on the organ involved. Gallbladder involvement may be in the form of biliary colic, acute cholecystitis, cholangitis and obstructive jaundice if extension occurs to the common bile duct. Laboratory examinations generally reveal anaemia and leukocytosis are indicating inflammatory nature of a tumour, but it has no specific tumour marker [13].

IMT of lung and liver can be managed conservatively if the preoperative histological diagnosis of IMT has been made. Regular follow-up is to be done to monitor resolution or progression of the condition [14]. Non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs and steroids are known to cause complete resolution of the disease [15]. However, there are no case reports of gallbladder IMT being treated by conservative means. Although they are benign tumours with no capacity of metastasis, they may infiltrate into surrounding tissues leading to recurrence even after resection [16]. These have been reported to occur between four to seven years after surgery [4, 17]. Therefore, long-term follow up is necessary even for patients who have been successfully treated by surgical resection.

In our case also patient was diagnosed as a case of symptomatic cholelithiasis with multiple episodes of biliary colic and planned for laparoscopic cholecystectomy. On histopathological examination, the incidental finding was inflammatory myofibroblast tumour. The patient was followed up by USG and CECT abdomen to see for any recurrence.

Conclusion

We aim to report and make surgeons, radiologists and pathologists aware of such rare cases like IMT to make a proper diagnosis. We also emphasise that although it is a benign tumour it has a recurrence and metastatic potential. It can be an incidental finding on laparoscopic cholecystectomy in case of gallbladder origin with the presentation as symptomatic cholelithiasis. These patients should be regularly followed up to keep watch for any recurrence and timely intervention.

Patient consent

Written informed consent was obtained from the patient for publication of this case report and any accompanying images. A copy of the written consent is available for review by the Editor-in-Chief of this journal.

Competing interests

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

References

1. Basak F, Hasbahceci M, Canbak T, Sisik A, Acar A, Yucel M et al. Incidental findings during routine pathological evaluation of gallbladder specimens: review of 1,747 elective laparoscopic cholecystectomy cases. *Ann R Coll Surg Engl* 2016;98:280-3.
2. Pettinato G, Manivel JC, De Rosa N, Dehner LP. Inflammatory myofibroblastic tumor (plasma cell granuloma). Clinicopathologic study of 20 cases with immunohistochemical and ultrastructural observations. *Am J Clin Pathol* 1990;94:538-46.
3. Behranwala KA, Straker P, Wan A, Fisher C, Thompson JN. Inflammatory myofibroblastic tumour of the gallbladder. *World J Surg Oncol* 2005;3:24.
4. Hagenstad CT, Klipatrick SE, Pettenati MJ, Sa-vage PD. Inflammatory myofibroblastic tumor with bone marrow involvement. A case report and review of literature. *Arch Pathol Lab Med* 2003;127:865-7.
5. Shek TW, Ng IO, Chan KW. Inflammatory pseudotumor of the liver. Report of four cases and review of literature. *Am J Surg Pathol* 1993;17:231-8.
6. Sawant S, Kasturi L, Amin A: Inflammatory myofibroblastic tumour. *Indian J Paediatr* 2002, 66:1001-2.
7. Buyukyavuz I, Karnak I, Haliloglu M, Senocak ME. Inflammatory myofibroblastic tumour of the extrahepatic bile ducts: an unusual cause of obstructive jaundice in children. *Eur J Paediatr Surg* 2003;13:421-4.
8. Muduly D, Deo SVS, Shukla NK, Manjuath NMC, Durgapal P, Kallianpur A. Inflammatory myofibroblastic tumor of gall bladder. *Trop gastroenterol* 2012;33:297-9.
9. Narla LD, Newman B, Spottswood SS, Narla S, Kolli R. Inflammatory pseudotumor. *RadioGraphics* 2003;23:719–29.
10. Umiker WO, Iverson L. Postinflammatory tumors of the lung; report of four cases simulating xanthoma, fibroma, or plasma cell tumor. *J Thorac Surg* 1954;28:55–63.
11. Meis-Kindblom JM, Kjellstrom C, Kindblom LJ: Inflammatory fibrosarcoma: update, reappraisal and perspective on its place in the spectrum of inflammatory myofibroblastic tumours. *Semin Diagn Pathol* 1998;15:133-43.
12. Fletcher CD: Myofibroblastic tumours: an update. *Verh Dtsch Ges Pathol* 1998;82:75-82.
13. Firat O, Ozturk S, Akalin T, Coker A. Inflammatory myofibroblastic tumour. *Can J Surg* 2009;52:E60-1.
14. Koea JB, Broadhurst GW, Rodgers MS, McCall JL. Inflammatory pseudotumor of the liver: demographics, diagnosis, and the case for nonoperative management. *J Am Coll Surg* 2003;196:226–35.
15. Vassiliadis T, Vougiouklis N, Patsiaoura K, Mpoumpoumaris A, Nikolaidis N, Giouleme O, et al. Inflammatory pseudotumor of the liver successfully treated with nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs: a challenge diagnosis for one not so rare entity. *Eur J Gastroenterol Hepatol* 2007;19:1016–20.
16. Coffin CM, Watterson J, Priest JR, Dehner LP. Extrapulmonary inflammatory myofibroblastic tumor (inflammatory pseudotumor). A clinicopathologic and immunohistochemical study of 84 cases. *Am J Surg Pathol* 1995;19:859-72.
17. Pecorella I, Ciardi A, Memeo L, Trombetta G, de Quarto A, de Simone P, et al. Inflammatory pseudotumour of the liver— evidence for malignant transformation. *Pathol Res Pract* 1999;195:115–20.
18. Kuo PH, Spooner S, Deol P, Monchamp T. Metastatic inflammatory myofibroblastic tumor imaged by PET/CT. *Clin Nucl Med* 2006;31:106–8.